

Prevalensi dan Karakteristik Hipotiroid pada Anak dengan Sindrom Down di RSUP Dr. Sardjito Yogyakarta (2020-2024): Studi Deskriptif Retrospektif

Baiq Rosyida Fauziah Effendy¹ (ORCID: 0009-0005-7256-941X), Tri Budi Hartomo² (ORCID: 0009-0006-4230-1161), Suryono Yudha Patria² (ORCID: 0000-0002-4821-0942)

Dari Program Studi Kedokteran¹ dan Departemen Ilmu Kesehatan Anak², Fakultas Kedokteran, Kesehatan Masyarakat, dan Keperawatan, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Latar belakang. Sindrom Down (Trisomi 21) merupakan kelainan genetik yang disebabkan oleh adanya satu kromosom 21 tambahan, yang mengakibatkan gangguan fisik, kognitif, dan medis. Salah satu komorbiditas endokrin yang paling sering ditemukan adalah hipotiroidisme, yang prevalensinya secara signifikan lebih tinggi pada populasi ini dibandingkan dengan populasi anak secara umum.

Tujuan. Mengetahui prevalensi dan karakteristik klinis hipotiroidisme pada anak dengan Sindrom Down yang berkunjung ke Poliklinik Endokrinologi Anak RSUP Dr. Sardjito Yogyakarta.

Metode. Penelitian deskriptif retrospektif ini menelaah rekam medis anak dengan Sindrom Down yang didiagnosis hipotiroidisme. Data prevalensi dikumpulkan dari Januari 2020 hingga Desember 2024. Karakteristik klinis, meliputi usia, jenis kelamin, kadar TSH dan FT4, tipe hipotiroidisme, gambaran klinis, serta komorbiditas, dianalisis dari Februari 2024 hingga Januari 2025.

Hasil. Dari 915 anak, sebanyak 278 anak (30,38%; IK 95%: 27,60–33,28%) didiagnosis hipotiroidisme pada periode 2020–2024. Pada analisis satu tahun, ditemukan 83 dari 172 anak (48,26%; IK 95%: 40,55–55,98%). Sebagian besar diagnosis ditegakkan secara klinis (74,7%), sedangkan sisanya dikonfirmasi dengan pemeriksaan kariotipe, dengan nondisjunction sebagai kelainan kromosom tersering. Gambaran klinis yang paling sering ditemukan adalah wajah dismorfik (57,83%), diikuti hernia umbilikal, telinga letak rendah, celah sandal, garis simian, dan hipotonia. Komorbiditas tersering meliputi penyakit jantung bawaan (22,89%), malnutrisi, dan keterlambatan perkembangan. Tipe hipotiroidisme yang paling banyak ditemukan adalah subklinis (77,11%), diikuti hipotiroidisme primer (10,84%) dan hipotiroidisme sentral (6,02%).

Kesimpulan. Hipotiroidisme memiliki prevalensi tinggi pada anak dengan Sindrom Down, terutama tipe subklinis. Skrining dan pemantauan rutin sangat penting untuk mencegah gangguan pertumbuhan dan perkembangan.

Kata kunci: hipotiroidisme, Sindrom Down, prevalensi, karakteristik klinis, studi retrospektif

Prevalence and Characteristics of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome at RSUP DR. Sardjito Yogyakarta (2020-2024): A Retrospective Descriptive Study

Baiq Rosyida Fauziah Effendy¹ (ORCID: 0009-0005-7256-941X), Tri Budi Hartomo² (ORCID: 0009-0006-4230-1161), Suryono Yudha Patria² (ORCID: 0000-0002-4821-0942)

From the Medical Study Program¹ and the Department of Child Health², Faculty of Medicine, Public Health, and Nursing, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia.

Background. Down syndrome (Trisomy 21) is a genetic disorder caused by an extra chromosome 21, leading to physical, cognitive, and medical impairments. One of the most frequent endocrine comorbidities is hypothyroidism, which is significantly more prevalent in this population than in the general pediatric population.

Objective. To determine the prevalence and clinical characteristics of hypothyroidism in children with Down syndrome attending the Pediatric Endocrinology Clinic at Dr. Sardjito General Hospital Yogyakarta.

Methods. This descriptive retrospective study reviewed medical records of children with Down syndrome diagnosed with hypothyroidism. Prevalence data were collected from January 2020 to December 2024. Clinical characteristics, including age, sex, TSH and FT4 levels, type of hypothyroidism, clinical features, and comorbidities, were analyzed from February 2024 to January 2025.

Result. Among 915 children, 278 (30.38%; 95% CI: 27.60–33.28%) were diagnosed with hypothyroidism between 2020 and 2024. In the one-year analysis, 83 of 172 children (48.26%; 95% CI: 40.55–55.98%) were identified. Most diagnoses were made clinically (74.7%), while the rest were confirmed by karyotyping, with nondisjunction being the most common chromosomal abnormality. The most frequent clinical features were dysmorphic facies (57.83%), followed by umbilical hernia, low-set ears, sandal gap, simian line, and hypotonia. The most common comorbidities included congenital heart disease (22.89%), undernutrition, and developmental delay. The most prevalent type of hypothyroidism was subclinical (77.11%), followed by primary (10.84%) and central hypothyroidism (6.02%).

Conclusion. Hypothyroidism is highly prevalent among children with Down syndrome, especially the subclinical type. Routine screening and monitoring are essential to prevent growth and developmental disorders.

Keywords: hypothyroidism, Down syndrome, prevalence, clinical characteristics, retrospective study

Alamat korespondensi: Baiq Rosyida Fauziah Effendy, Fakultas Kedokteran, Kesehatan Masyarakat, dan Keperawatan, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Jl. Farmako Sekip Utara, Yogyakarta 55281, Indonesia. Tel. +62 821-1554-0109; E-mail: rosyidafauziah17@gmail.com

Down syndrome (DS), or Trisomy 21, is a genetic disorder caused by an extra copy of chromosome 21, resulting in intellectual disabilities and various health problems^{1,2}. Individuals with DS typically exhibit characteristic facial features and developmental delays³. Globally, Down syndrome occurs in about 1 in 700 live births and is the most common genetic cause of developmental delay, with the risk increasing with maternal age from approximately 1 in 1,250 at age 25 to 1 in 400 at age 35 and 1 in 100 at age 40, although 80% of affected babies are born to mothers younger than 35 years⁴. In Indonesia, the 2018 Basic Health Research (Risksedas) reported a prevalence of DS at 0.21% among children aged 24–59 months⁵.

Children with DS are prone to various medical complications, including congenital heart defects^{6,7}, gastrointestinal abnormalities, and endocrine disorders, particularly thyroid dysfunction⁸. Hypothyroidism is the most common endocrine disorder in this population and may be either congenital or acquired^{9,10}. Congenital hypothyroidism is typically due to thyroid hypoplasia or ectopy, whereas acquired hypothyroidism, often associated with autoimmune thyroiditis, tends to emerge with increasing age^{11,12}.

The clinical signs and symptoms of hypothyroidism often resemble the typical features of DS, making diagnosis challenging without routine screening^{13,14,15}. Therefore, the American Academy of Pediatrics recommends thyroid function screening at birth, 6 months, 12 months, and annually thereafter^{16,17}.

Although numerous global studies have addressed this issue, data on hypothyroidism in children with DS in Indonesia remain limited. This study aims to assess the prevalence and clinical characteristics of hypothyroidism in children with Down syndrome undergoing evaluation at the Pediatric Endocrinology Clinic of Dr. Sardjito General Hospital, Yogyakarta.

Methods

This study employed a retrospective descriptive design with a quantitative approach. Data were obtained from the medical records of children with Down syndrome who underwent thyroid function tests at the Pediatric Endocrinology Clinic of Dr. Sardjito General Hospital, Yogyakarta. Five-year prevalence data, covering the period from January

2020 to December 2024, were collected from the hospital's Medical Records Department. Meanwhile, one-year prevalence data and clinical characteristics were collected from the Pediatric Endocrinology Clinic for the period of February 2024 to January 2025. Data collection was conducted in July 2025 after receiving ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Public Health, and Nursing, Universitas Gadjah Mada.

The study subjects included children aged 0 to 18 years with a confirmed diagnosis of Down syndrome who had undergone thyroid function testing, specifically TSH and FT4 measurements. Children with other genetic disorders or incomplete medical records were excluded. All patients who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study using a total sampling technique.

The variables examined in this study included age, sex, TSH and FT4 levels, and thyroid status based on laboratory results. Hormone levels were assessed using immunochemical methods such as ECLIA or CLIA, and results were interpreted according to age-specific reference ranges¹⁷. Based on TSH and FT4 values, thyroid status was classified into several categories. Primary hypothyroidism was defined by elevated TSH and low FT4 levels. Subclinical hypothyroidism presented with elevated TSH but normal FT4. Central hypothyroidism showed normal or low TSH with low FT4. Patients with normal TSH and FT4 levels were categorized as euthyroid.

Data collection was conducted by reviewing physical or electronic medical records and entering the relevant information into a structured extraction form developed by the researcher and reviewed by the academic supervisor. TSH and FT4 values were carefully recorded and double-checked for accuracy. The collected data were processed and analyzed descriptively using Microsoft Excel and SPSS, and results were presented in the form of frequency tables, percentages, means, and standard deviations, as appropriate.

Throughout the research process, patient privacy and data confidentiality were strictly maintained by excluding all personal identifiers. Data collection and analysis process, patient confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by excluding any personal identifiers.

Results

1. Prevalence of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome

Between January 2020 and December 2024, a total of 915 children with Down syndrome were recorded at the Pediatric Endocrinology Clinic of Dr. Sardjito General Hospital. Of these, 278 were diagnosed with hypothyroidism, resulting in a prevalence of 30.38% (95% CI: 27.60–33.28%). The prevalence was slightly higher in males (32.42%) than females (28.18%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.38$).

In the period from February 2024 to January 2025, 83 of 172 children with Down syndrome (48.26%; 95% CI: 40.55–55.98%) were found to have hypothyroidism, indicating a significant increase compared to the previous period ($p < 0.0001$). No significant sex-based difference was observed during this period ($p > 0.05$). (Table 1).

2. Diagnostic Methods and Karyotype Results

The diagnosis of Down syndrome in children from February 2024 to January 2025 was made through clinical evaluation and cytogenetic testing (karyotyping). Of the 172 subjects, 117 children (68.02%; 95% CI: 60.08%–75.09%) were clinically diagnosed, while 55 children (31.98%; 95% CI: 24.91%–39.92%) underwent karyotyping. The difference in proportions between these diagnostic methods was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$), indicating that the proportion of children diagnosed clinically was much higher than those undergoing karyotyping.

Among the 55 children who underwent karyotyping, the majority were found to have nondisjunction, totaling 46 children (83.64%; 95% CI: 72.00%–91.41%). Additionally, 6 children (10.90%; 95% CI: 5.11%–21.97%) were identified with Robertsonian translocation, and 3 children (5.46%; 95% CI: 1.87%–14.86%) with mosaicism. The distribution of karyotype results shows that nondisjunction was the most common chromosomal abnormality found in children with Down syndrome in this study. The detailed results are presented in Table 2.

3. Demographic Characteristics and Diagnostic Methods

This subsection presents the findings related to children with Down syndrome and hypothyroidism recorded in the pediatric endocrinology outpatient registry at Dr. Sardjito General Hospital, with data traced further through the electronic medical records (e-MR). The analyzed subjects were diagnosed between February 2024 and January 2025, comprising a total of 83 children. Demographic characteristics and diagnostic methods of the subjects are presented in Table 3.

Based on sex distribution, there were 45 boys (54.2%) and 38 girls (45.8%). Statistical analysis showed no significant difference in sex proportions ($p = 0.44$), indicating that the male-female distribution occurred randomly and did not reflect a specific trend in this population.

The mean age of the subjects was 3.73 ± 3.47 years, with a 95% confidence interval (CI) between 2.98 and 4.48 years. When categorized by age, most of the subjects were aged ≤ 1 year, totaling 58 children (69.88%; 95% CI: 59.51%–78.97%). The >1 –5 years age group included 21 children (25.30%; 95% CI: 17.11%–35.50%), while the >5 years group included 4 children (4.82%; 95% CI: 1.89%–11.75%). The p -value of 0.0013 indicates a statistically significant difference between age groups.

4. Clinical Characteristics of Subjects

This subsection presents an analysis of the clinical characteristics of children with Down syndrome diagnosed with hypothyroidism, based on electronic medical records (e-MR) from the outpatient clinic at Dr. Sardjito General Hospital. Data were collected through manual review of each pediatric endocrinology outpatient visit during the period of February 2024 to January 2025. All recorded data were obtained from physicians' clinical assessments documented during both initial and follow-up visits in the e-MR system. The distribution of clinical findings in the study subjects is presented in Table 4.

The majority of subjects (57.8%) showed dysmorphic facial features such as epicanthus, flat nasal bridge, or low-set ears, which are characteristic of Down syndrome and consistently documented in the e-MR. This finding had a 95% confidence interval (CI) ranging from 47.2% to 68.5%.

Other findings supporting the diagnosis of hypothyroidism included hypotonia (7.2%; 95% CI: 2.4%–15.9%) and large anterior fontanelle (2.4%; 95% CI: 0.3%–8.4%), although these characteristics were nonspecific and found only in a small proportion of subjects. Clinical signs related to delayed motor development, such as head lag, were also identified in a small proportion of subjects (1.2%; 95% CI: 0.03%–6.5%).

5. Comorbidities of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome

Comorbidity data were obtained from clinical diagnosis records in outpatient medical charts. Identified comorbidities included cardiac abnormalities, gastrointestinal and orofacial disorders, infections, respiratory issues, nutritional status, developmental delays, and genitourinary and neurological disorders. The distribution of comorbidities is presented in Table 5.

Congenital heart disease was the most common comorbidity, with atrial septal defect (ASD) observed in 22.89% of subjects (95% CI: 13.85%–31.93%), followed by patent ductus arteriosus (15.66%) and ventricular septal defect (12.05%).

Gastrointestinal and orofacial issues such as umbilical hernia (10.84%) and constipation (7.23%) were also commonly found. Respiratory issues such as pneumonia were found in 8.43% of subjects.

Nutritional disorders included underweight (21.69%), moderate malnutrition (16.87%), and stunting (14.46%). Global developmental delay was found in 8.43% of subjects. Further details are shown in Table 5

6. TSH Levels Distribution by Age Group

The distribution of TSH levels in children with Down syndrome and hypothyroidism was analyzed based on age group and is presented in Table 6.

Most age groups showed a significant proportion of elevated TSH levels. In the 0–7 days age group, all subjects had TSH levels above the normal range (100%). In the >7 days–3 months group, 90% had elevated TSH. In the >3 months–1 year and >1–5 years groups, the proportions of elevated TSH were 75.86% and 74.29%, respectively. However, there were no statistically significant differences between age groups ($p > 0.05$).

7. Free T4 Levels Distribution by Age Group

Analysis of FT4 levels was performed by age group, as shown in Table 7. The majority of subjects had FT4 levels within the normal range.

In the 0–7 days group, only one of three children (33.33%) had low FT4 levels. In the >3 months–1 year group, 13.79% of children showed low FT4, and in the >1–5 years group, 22.86% had low FT4 levels. No significant differences were found between age groups ($p > 0.05$).

8. Distribution of Hypothyroidism Types by Age Group

The most common type of hypothyroidism was subclinical hypothyroidism (77.11%), followed by primary hypothyroidism (10.84%) and central hypothyroidism (6.02%). Euthyroid status was also found in 6.02% of subjects. This distribution was based on the interpretation of TSH and FT4 levels by the researchers and is presented in Table 8.

There was no statistically significant difference in the distribution of hypothyroidism types across age groups ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The prevalence of hypothyroidism in children with Down syndrome in this study reached 30.38% over a five-year period and increased to 48.26% in the most recent one-year period. This prevalence is considerably higher compared to the general population, consistent with previous reports stating that the incidence of hypothyroidism in Down syndrome is 1 in 113 to 1 in 141 live births, which is approximately 28–35 times higher than in the general population^{9,10}. The high prevalence underscores the importance of routine thyroid screening, even in asymptomatic children, as thyroid dysfunction often presents subclinically and may go undetected without laboratory evaluation.

The significant increase in prevalence during the most recent year is likely related to heightened clinician awareness of early thyroid evaluation and improved access to laboratory services. Moreover, the high proportion of subclinical hypothyroidism diagnoses likely contributed to the increased detection

rate. Subclinical hypothyroidism is the most commonly encountered thyroid disorder in children with Down syndrome, characterized by elevated TSH levels while FT4 remains within normal limits^{14,16}. This condition may be transient or persistent and has the potential to develop into overt hypothyroidism if not monitored regularly.

This study found no significant difference in hypothyroidism prevalence between sexes, both over the five-year and one-year periods. This supports prior findings that thyroid dysfunction in children with Down syndrome does not display sex predilection¹⁷, which contrasts with the general population, where females are more prone to thyroid disorders⁸.

Most subjects in this study exhibited elevated TSH levels, especially in the under-one-year age group, while FT4 levels generally remained within the normal range. This emphasizes the importance of early detection, as thyroid dysfunction can already be present in laboratory findings before clinical symptoms appear^{8,18}. The lack of statistically significant differences in TSH and FT4 levels across age groups is consistent with previous studies reporting that thyroid dysfunction can occur at any age with a wide range of clinical presentations¹¹.

Clinical features commonly seen in Down syndrome, such as dysmorphic facies, hypotonia, macroglossia, and developmental delay, were present in most subjects. However, since many of these signs are also inherent to Down syndrome itself, it is difficult to distinguish hypothyroidism based on clinical signs alone. Hence, TSH and FT4 measurements are essential for objective diagnosis¹³.

The most frequently observed comorbidities in this study were congenital heart defects, particularly atrial septal defect (ASD), patent ductus arteriosus (PDA), and ventricular septal defect (VSD). This is consistent with previous epidemiological data indicating that 40–60% of children with Down syndrome have congenital heart anomalies⁸. Nutritional issues such as underweight and stunting were also commonly found, potentially resulting from metabolic disturbances due to hypothyroidism or from other comorbid conditions such as recurrent respiratory infections and feeding difficulties¹⁸.

Karyotype analysis in a subset of subjects revealed that nondisjunction was the most common chromosomal abnormality, followed by Robertsonian translocation and mosaicism. This finding aligns with

existing literature stating that over 90% of Down syndrome cases are caused by nondisjunction². Although karyotyping is not always routinely performed in clinical practice, it remains important for confirming the genetic diagnosis and providing appropriate family counseling regarding recurrence risk in future pregnancies^{15,19}.

A limitation in this study was that, as a retrospective analysis, it depended on the completeness of electronic medical records, which may have led to underreporting of certain clinical and laboratory characteristics. In addition, occasional inconsistencies in EMR formatting posed technical challenges during data extraction.

The recommendation based on this study is that routine thyroid screening is strongly recommended to begin in the neonatal period and be continued at 6–12-month intervals with age-specific interpretation of TSH and FT4^{8,17}. Strengthening integrated medical record systems and conducting future prospective studies with larger cohorts and thyroid autoantibody testing are advised to further clarify the natural course and etiology of hypothyroidism in this population. Education of parents and caregivers remains essential to ensure adherence to long-term monitoring and timely intervention.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrated a high burden of thyroid dysfunction, predominantly subclinical hypothyroidism, among children with Down syndrome, particularly during the first five years of life. The rising prevalence observed in the most recent year suggests that earlier and more consistent screening practices are increasingly being implemented and are effective in identifying cases that may otherwise remain undetected.

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Table 1. Prevalence of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome

Period	Sex	Total DS	DS with HT Prevalence (%)	95% CI	p value
Jan 2020 – Dec 2024 (5 years)	Total	915	278 (30.38%)	27.60% – 33.28%	0.38
	F	440	124 (28.18%)	24.14% – 32.58%	
	M	475	154 (32.42%)	28.23% – 36.83 %	
Feb 2024 – Jan 2025 (12 months)	Total	172	83 (48.26%)	40.55% – 55.98%	<0.0001
	F	75	38 (50.67%)	39.08% – 62.21%	0.78
	M	97	45 (46.39%)	36.33% – 56.74%	

Note: DS = Down syndrome; HT = Hypothyroidism; F = Female; M = Male

Table 2. Diagnostic Methods and Karyotype Results in Children with Down Syndrome (2024-2025)

Diagnosis Method for DS (12 months)	Total	Percentage (%)	95% CI	p value
- Karyotyping	55	31.98%	24.91% – 39.92%	<0.0001
- Clinical	117	68.02%	60.08% – 75.09%	
Karyotyping result (n=55)				
- Nondisjunction	46	83.64%	72.00% – 91.41%	
- Robertsonian translocation	6	10.90%	5.11% – 21.97%	
- Mosaicism	3	5.46%	1.87% – 14.86%	

Note: DS = Down syndrome

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics and Diagnostic Methods of Study Subjects

Characteristics	Total (n = 83) Mean ± SD	Percentage (%) Mean ± SD	95% CI	p value
Sex			-	0.44
- Male	45	54.2%		
- Female	38	45.8%		
Age (years)	3.73 ± 3.47	-	2.98 – 4.48 years	0.0013
- ≤ 1 year	58	69.88%	59.51% – 78.97%	
- >1 – 5 years	21	25.30%	17.11% – 35.50 %	
- > 5 years	4	4.82%	1.89% – 11.75%	
Diagnosis Method for DS			-	<0.0001
- Karyotyping	21	25.3%	16.0% – 34.6%	
- Clinical	62	74.7%	65.4% – 84.0%	
Karyotyping Result	n = 21			
- Nondisjunction	16	76.2%	58.0% – 94.4%	
- Robertsonian translocation	4	19.0%	2.5% – 35.5 %	
- Mosaicism	1	4.8%	0.0% – 14.0%	

Table 4. Clinical Characteristics of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome

Clinical Characteristics	Total	Percentage (%)	95% CI
Facies dysmorphic	48	57.83%	47.20% – 68.50%
Umbilical hernia	9	10.84%	4.2% – 17.50%
Low set ear	9	10.84%	4.20% – 17.50%
Sandal gap	7	8.43%	2.50% – 14.40%
Simian line	6	7.23%	1.70% – 12.80%
Hypotonia	6	7.23%	1.70% – 12.80%
Macroglossia	5	6.02%	0.90% – 11.10%
Heart murmur	5	6.02%	0.90% – 11.10%
Microcephaly	4	4.82%	0.20% – 0.94%

Table 5. Comorbidities of Hypothyroidism in Children with Down Syndrome

Comorbidities	Total	Percentage (%)	95% CI
Heart	19	22.89%	13.85% – 31.93%
Underweight	18	21.69%	12.95% – 30.43%
Undernutrition	14	16.87%	9.06% – 24.68%
Stunting	12	14.46%	7.12% – 21.80%
Pneumonia	7	8.43%	2.38% – 14.48%
Global developmental delay	7	8.43%	2.38% – 14.48%
Nystagmus	5	6.01%	0.90% – 11.14%

Table 6. Distribution of TSH Levels by Age Group in Children with Down Syndrome and Hypothyroidism

Age Group	n	TSH (μ IU/mL)		p value
		Number High (%)	95% CI	
0 – 7 days	3	3 (100.00%)	100.00%	Reference group
> 7 days – 3 months	10	9 (90.00%)	55.50% – 99.75 %	0.500
> 3 months – 1 year	29	22 (75.86%)	57.20% – 88.90 %	0.197
> 1 year – 5 years	35	26 (74.29%)	56.70% – 87.50%	0.167
> 5 years – 12 years	5	4 (80.00%)	28.40% – 99.50%	0.467
> 12 years – 18 years	1	1 (100.00%)	100.00%	1.000

Note: TSH = Thyroid Stimulating Hormone

Table 7. Distribution of Free T4 Levels by Age Group in Children with Down Syndrome and Hypothyroidism

Age Group	n	Free T4 (ng/dL)		p value
		Number Low (%)	95% CI	
0 – 7 days	3	1 (33.33%)	100.00%	Reference group
> 7 days – 3 months	10	1 (10.00%)	6.15% – 79.23%	0.423
> 3 months – 1 year	29	4 (3.79%)	1.79% – 40.42%	0.410
> 1 year – 5 years	35	8 (22.86%)	5.50% – 30.56%	1.000
> 5 years – 12 years	5	0 (0.00%)	12.07% – 39.02	0.375
> 12 years – 18 years	1	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 43.45%	1.000

Table 8. Distribution of Types of Hypothyroidism by Age Group in Children with Down Syndrome (n = 83)

Type of HT	Age Group (n=83)	n (%)	95% CI	Total (%) 95 % CI p value
Subclinical HT	A	2 (66.67%)	9.43% – 99.16%	64 (77,11 %) (66.90%–85.20%) 0.842
	B	8 (80.00%)	44.39% – 97.48%	
	C	22 (75.80%)	56.50% – 89.70%	
	D	27 (77.14%)	60.19% – 89.58%	
	E	4 (80.00%)	28.36% – 99.49%	
	F	1 (100.00%)	2.50% – 97.50%	
Primary HT	A	1 (33.33%)	0.84% – 90.57%	9 (10.84 %) (5.79%–19.42%) 0.114
	B	1 (10.00%)	0.25% – 44.50%	
	C	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 11.91%	
	D	7 (20.00%)	8.40% – 36.94 %	
	E	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 52.18%	
	F	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 97.50%	
Central HT	A	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 70.76%	5 (6.02 %) (2.60%–13.30%) 0.425
	B	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 30.85%	
	C	4 (13.79%)	3.91% – 31.66%	
	D	1 (2.86%)	0.07% – 14.92%	
	E	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 97.50%	
	F	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 97.50%	
Euthyroid	A	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 70.76%	5 (6.02 %) (2.60%–13.30%) 0.448
	B	1 (10.00%)	0.25% – 44.50%	
	C	3 (10.35%)	2.20% – 27.35%	
	D	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 10.00%	
	E	1 (20.00%)	0.00% – 52.18%	
	F	0 (0.00%)	0.00% – 97.50%	

Note: HT = Hypothyroidism; Group A = 0–7 days (n =3); B = >7 days–3 months (n=10); C = > 3 months–1 year (n=29); D = > 1 year–5 years (n=35); E = > 5 years–12 years (n=5); F = > 12 years–18 years (n=1)